

PRESENTING INDIVIDUAL SPEECH AND THE SOCIO-HISTORICAL CONTEXT IN THE TRANSLATION OF HISTORICAL WORKS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17678371>

Abstract

The article dicusses how the spirit, period-specific culture, and linguistic style of a historical novel can be conveyed through characters' speech during the translation process. It emphasizes the importance of selecting words and expressions that correspond to the work's style theme, and the nature of events, while preserving the national and historical context.

Key words: translation, historical novel, character speech, period culture, national spirit, artistic-stylistic harmony, translator's skill. Linguistic coherence.

A literary work can be written in various styles and for different purposes. This largely depends on the period depicted in the book, the chosen theme, and the nature of the events. If these characteristics of a work selected for translation are not clearly identified, it becomes impossible to find a key that corresponds to its spirit; ultimately, even if the work is transferred into another language, it will not reveal its "charm" to the new readers. Consequently, the intended purpose of the translation may not be achieved. Establishing the quality of the translation and the translator's skill on a scientific basis, and examining the translation in terms of artistic-stylistic harmony with the original text, are among the main objectives. In this context, rendering words specific to the national identity in the translation is considered an essential aspect.

Renowned translation scholar G. Salomov, discussing the role of the translator, notes the following: the translator's task is to convey the work from one language into another without damaging its spirit, content, or tone, while finding words and expressions in their own language that fully correspond to the original text in terms of imagery, meaning, rhythm, tone, and the emotions and impressions it evokes in the reader [1].

The translation of historical novels demands a high level of skill to preserve the work's unique spirit. In particular, it is essential to accurately reflect the characters' personalities and the period's cultural context through their speech. Taking this into account, the following aspects should be considered when translating the speech of characters:

- preserving the cultural and historical spirit;
- adapting dialects and folk styles into the target language;
- recreating speech that reflects the character's personality;

- translating proverbs and folk expressions with semantic adaptation;
- maintaining cultural and linguistic coherence.

In the process of translating historical novels, it is crucial to deeply understand cultural features and present them in a way familiar to the reader. Through characters' speech, their era, social position, and regional characteristics should be conveyed. Recreating language means that reflects the spirit of the period is one of the translator's main responsibilities. At this point, let us consider an example from the novel "O'tkan Kunlar" ("Bygone days"):

"Otabekning tasallo berishi bilan Hasanali undan qo'l tortdi ersa-da, biroq undan hayajon, yig'i hali arimagan edi.

- Adab! – deb qichqirdi Musulmonqul, so'ngra o'ziga qarab qo'l bog'lag'an Hasanalidan so'radi:

- Sen kimning chopari?
- Normuhammad qushbegining.
- Qayerdan?
- Toshkanddan, taqsir." [2]

The speech of the characters presented above is rendered in the English translation of the work by I.Tukhtasinov and others as follows:

Otabek comforted Hasanali, only then he released Otabek from his hug, but still he was excited, there were tears in his eyes.

- "Be quiet!"- Musulmonqul shouted, and then asked Hasanali:
- "Whose courier are you?"
- "Nurmukhammad Qushbegi's."
- "Where are you from?"
- "From Tashkent, sir." [3]

If we pay attention to the above translation, the original author conveys the spirit of the era and the social status of the characters to the reader through words such as "tasallo" (consolation), "adab" (etiquette), "chopar" (herald), "qushbegi" (a title for a military or court official), and "taqsir" (sir/young master). A reader, upon reading the text, can understand Muslimqul's coarseness, arrogance, and, in some cases, injustice from his usage of expressions like "adab" and "kimning choparsan?" Furthermore, words like "chopar," "qushbegi," and "taqsir" naturally convey the historical period and the era of the khanate. Thus, faithfully translating such idiomatic and culturally loaded words and expressions is a primary responsibility of the translator. Without them, the work loses its charm and vivid depiction. Historical accuracy and the expression of the spirit of the era become blurred. This delicate issue has been skillfully addressed in the English translation

by I. To'xtasinov and others. However, in one instance, the word "taqsir" in the original text was translated as "sir." In our opinion, this translation fails to convey the historical and cultural essence of the original, as the English "sir" is used to politely address someone[4]. While it may reflect Hasanali Muslimqul's politeness, it loses the sense of era, nationality, and historical context. In our view, it would have been appropriate to render the word "taqsir" from the original text through transcription and provide an explanatory note at the bottom of the page. Referring to examples of translated texts into Uzbek, we often see "sir" given in transcription. Only then can English readers understand the connection to the original. This raises the natural question: why should English-speaking readers not perceive our "taqsir"?

Additionally, the original expression "o'ziga qarab qo'l bog'lagan" was not accurately conveyed. By using this phrase, the author illustrates that Hasanali, in front of Muslimqul, is in a vulnerable position, hesitating to provoke his anger while seeking justice and mercy. This descriptive nuance is missing in the translation.

When reviewing translations, we also pay attention to this exact passage in another English translation by translator Mark Reese.

"Even though Otabek tried to calm him, Hasanali could not help himself from loudly shedding tears.

"Where is your etiquette?" shouted Musulmanqul while clenching his fists and looking about. "Whose courier are you?"

"I am assigned to Nur Muhammad Qushbegi." "From what region?"

"From Tashkent, Taksir." [5]

If we pay attention to the translated text above, the translator could not fully convey the meaning understood from the original text. In the original text, the sentence "Otabekning tasallo berishi bilan Hasanali undan qo'l tortdi ersa-da, biroq undan hayajon, yig'i hali arimagan edi" was translated as "Even though Otabek tried to calm him, Hasanali could not help himself from loudly shedding tears." That is, Hasanali's emotional state of crying with excitement was described as "loudly shedding tears." In doing so, the translation presents Hasanali as if he were crying loudly without fear of anyone in the palace. In contrast, the author describes Otabek's potentially fatal action as something Hasanali fully understands, which is why his state is depicted as "shedding tears with excitement." In subsequent scenes, Hasanali, without any unnecessary movements, respectfully kept his hands to himself and showed fear toward Musulmankul, which was not reflected; instead, the translation depicts him

clenching Musulmankul's fists. Indeed, in this scenario, clenching fists and standing with anger may suit Musulmankul, but this depiction does not correspond to the original. When Musulmankul says "Odob saqlang" for interrogation, it makes more sense as "Be quiet" in English. Here, I. Tohtasinov's translation, "Be quiet!", can be considered adequate. The word "taqsir" in the translation is, in our opinion, translated in the most appropriate way and effectively conveys the spirit of the time. In Mark E. Reese's translation, special notes are provided at the end for words characteristic of historicity and nationality. For instance, the word "Taksir" is explained in footnotes as literally translating to "sir" or "master." [6]

The same passage has been translated into English by translator K. Yermakova as follows:

"Atabek hushed him, then pushed him aside. So then asked Khasanali as he backed away.

"Behave yourself!" bellowed Musulman Kul. Khasanali managed a respect him distance and Musulman Kul asked:

"Who sent you?"

"Nur mohammed Qushbegi."

"Where from?"

"From Tashkent, taksyr." [7]

In the translation, Hasanali is depicted as if Otabek asked him to step back, while in the original text, Otabek only tried to calm him and did not ask him to move back. Hasanali's emotional tears were not described in the translation. However, the previously omitted detail, "Hasanali keeping his hands folded," was beautifully rendered as "managed a respect him distance," conveying respect. In Uzbek culture, folding hands indicates respect, a gesture akin to a greeting or salutation. To express Musulmankul's shouting to calm them, translator K. Ermakova used the word "bellowed" in English, accurately conveying the situation to English readers. The English verb "to shout" merely means "to cry out," "To bellow - to make a deep sound that a bull and other large animals make" [8] whereas "to bellow" implies producing a deep sound like a bull or other large animals, thus conveying a stronger, negative connotation.

To conclude, in translating historical works, it is crucial not only to convey the content of events but also to reflect characters' speech, individuality, and period-appropriate language. In some cases, the unique speech of historical novel characters may be lost due to insufficient attention to the historical context and

linguistic style of the period. The language of characters in historical works should reflect their social status, culture, and the spirit of the era.

Used literature

- 1.Salomov G'. Til va tarjima. -Tashkent.: Fan, 1966 y., p.86.
- 2.Qodiriy A. Otkan kunlar. (Ozbeklar turmushudan tarixiy roman), Toshkent: "Navroz", 2019, p.126.
- 3.Qodiriy, Abdulla. The Days Gone By: Novel. Translators: I. M. To'htasinov, O. M. Mo'minov, A. A. Khamidov. -T.: "Mashhur press", 2017, p.124.
- 4.Macmillan English dictionary for advanced learners. Bloomsbury Publishing Plc. 2002. p.1334.
- 5.Abdullah Qodiriy, Bygone Days, translated by Mark E. Reese, Library of Congress Control Number 2019914747, 2019, p.156.
- 6.Abdullah Qodiriy, Bygone Days, translated by Mark E. Reese, Library of Congress Control Number 2019914747, 2019, p.636. Note number – 52.
- 7.Abdulla Qadiri, Days Gone By, Translated by Carol Ermakova, Nouveau monde, Paris, 2018, p.119.
- 8.Macmillan English dictionary for advanced learners. Bloomsbury Publishing Plc. 2002. p.114.

